

Studies in Condensed Phosphates. Part V. Reaction of Sodium Metaphosphate with Ferric Salt in Solution

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Attempts to synthesise compounds with the general formula $(\text{Na}_x\text{Fe}_{1-x/3}\text{PO}_3)_n$ always yield heterogeneous products with extremely slow rate of solution.

Physico-chemical studies of the reaction between ferric chloride and sodium metaphosphate yield a solid with the composition $\text{Fe}_2(\text{OH})_3(\text{PO}_3)_3$, the composition of which is not affected by dilution. Comparative reactions of orthophosphate have also been investigated.

The complexes of ferric salt with orthophosphate ions in solution have been studied by several workers¹. Recently Banerjee² has reported the formation of two complexes, i.e., $[\text{Fe}(\text{HPO}_4)_4]^{+}$ and $[\text{Fe}(\text{HPO}_4)_2]^{-}$ in solution from conductometric titration of phosphoric acid and ferric chloride. Kantzer³ has reported the formation of some complexes with sodium tri- and tetra-metaphosphate and ferric chloride in solution and synthesised the derivatives with the formulas $\text{Na}_3[\text{FeCl}_2(\text{PO}_3)_4]$ and $\text{Fe}[\text{FeCl}_2(\text{PO}_3)_4]$ as light rose-coloured powders, slightly soluble in water.

In earlier communications⁴ from these laboratories, the preparation and properties of mixed metaphosphates with the general formula $(\text{Na}_x\text{M}_{1-x/2}\text{PO}_3)_n$ (where M is Ca, Ba, Zn, Pb, or Cu and 2 is the valency of metal ions) have been described. Sodium metaphosphate has been reported to sequester ferric ions in solution so effectively that the sensitive ferrocyanide and thiocyanate tests are no longer indicated. Attempts were made to prepare mixed metaphosphates by heating together the following reaction mixture:

at 900° for 2 to 3 hours, but only a portion of ferric salt appeared to be dissolved even when the molar ratio of $\text{NaH}_2\text{PO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was increased to 9, so that a compound of the empirical formula $[\text{Na}_9\text{Fe}(\text{PO}_3)_{12}]_n$ could be obtained. The yellowish melt was not quite uniform and clear; it had a few specks of undissolved material which remained suspended in the chilled glass; it has a light violet colour. A few clear pieces of the chilled glass were taken for analysis. The solubility of the glass in water is very low. On analysis it was found to have a Fe : P ratio of 1:17, confirming the heterogeneous character of the melt. Due to its very low solubility in water, further work with the solid could not be carried out.

1. Weinland and Engsaber, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1914, **84**, 340; Jensen, *ibid.*, 1934, **221**, 1; Lanford and Kiehl, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, **64**, 291.
2. *This Journal*, 1950, **27**, 417.
3. *Compt. rend.*, 1945, **220**, 661.
4. Mehrotra and Gupta, *J. Polymer Sci.*, 1961, **54**, 613.

On treating a ferric chloride solution with sodium metaphosphate solution, a white precipitate begins to form and the amount goes on increasing until about 1.5 moles of the metaphosphate have been added. On further addition of sodium metaphosphate, the precipitate tends to dissolve; a clear solution is obtained when about 4.5 moles of the metaphosphate have been added.

Conductometric and potentiometric titrations of ferric chloride with sodium metaphosphate solution indicated a sharp inflection point at the molar ratio of $\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot \frac{1}{n}(\text{NaPO}_3)_n$ at 1:1.5. The sharp rise in conductance and fall in $p\text{H}$ in this portion of the curve can be easily explained on the basis of the following possible reaction in solution:

The formation of a precipitate of this composition was confirmed by analysis. In order to ensure that this particular composition of the precipitate was not obtained due to initial hydrolysis of ferric ions, the precipitation and analyses were repeated in solutions of varying concentrations ($M/10$ to $M/500$) and the composition of the precipitate was found to remain unaffected.

After the addition of 1.5 moles, the precipitate begins to dissolve and both the $p\text{H}$ and the resistance of the solution increase sharply, indicating equilibria of the type:

The correctness of the above appears to be indicated by a weak inflection point at about 4.5 equivalents of sodium metaphosphate in both titration curves as well as in the reverse conductometric titration curves (Figs. 1—3). The formation of a precipitate with the composition $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_{1.5}(\text{PO}_3)_{1.5}$ is rather unusual and it could be written in the form $\text{Fe}(\text{HPO}_4)_{1.5}$ or $\text{Fe}_2(\text{HPO}_4)_3$. Attempts to decide between the two possibilities by leaching the precipitate with concentrated sodium chloride in the hope of extracting the phosphate content in the form of sodium salt and identifying it by chromatographic analysis failed due to highly insoluble nature of the precipitate. It was shown, however, that on titrating ferric chloride with a solution of disodium orthophosphate, maximum precipitate occurred at 1:1 molar ratio and the precipitate corresponded in composition to FePO_4 . The nature and amount of the precipitate did not appear to change on the addition of the excess of sodium metaphosphate solution. The above observation indicates that a reaction of the following type occurs:

The correctness of the above assumption is confirmed by electrometric titration of a ferric chloride solution with a solution of disodium orthophosphate, when $p\text{H}$ of the solution is crossed up to the addition of 10 moles of the disodium orthophosphate and then it begins to rise sharply, probably due to the equilibrium:

as is seen from Fig. 4.

TABLE I

System: $\text{FeCl}_3\text{—H}_2\text{O—NaPO}_3$. $M/250\text{-FeCl}_3$ (25 ml) solution was titrated conductometrically against $M/10\text{-(NaPO}_3)_n$ solution.

Sp. cond. $\times 10^3$.	Vol.	Remarks.
0.1885	0.0 ml	Solution
0.2017	0.5	Ppt. forms
0.2126	1.0	
0.2182	1.5	Probably ppt. is max.
0.2120	2.0	Ppt. starts dissolving
0.2001	2.5	
0.1919	3.0	
0.1861	3.5	
0.1857	4.0	
0.1870	4.5	Almost disappears
0.1875	5.0	

TABLE II

System: $\text{FeCl}_3\text{—H}_2\text{O—NaPO}_3$. $M/500\text{-FeCl}_3$ (50 ml) was titrated against $M/10\text{-(NaPO}_3)_n$ solution.

Vol.	pH.	Remarks.
0.00 ml	2.80	
0.50	2.68	Ppt.
1.00	2.60	Ppt. increases
1.50	2.58	Probably maximum
1.75	2.58	
2.00	2.61	
2.50	2.69	
3.00	2.78	
3.50	2.86	
4.00	2.93	
4.50	3.00	Almost disappears
5.00	3.07	
6.00	3.20	
6.50	3.25	
7.00	3.30	
7.50	3.34	
8.00	3.39	
8.50	3.42	

EXPERIMENTAL

All the reagents used were of pure grade. Ferric chloride solution was made by standardisation. Readings were taken at $25^\circ \pm 0.05^\circ$ unless mentioned otherwise. The description of apparatus has already been given in an earlier communication⁴. Extra pure water was used for all measurements.

TABLE III

System: $\text{NaPO}_3-\text{H}_2\text{O}-\text{FeCl}_3$. $M/500-(\text{NaPO}_3)_n$ solution (50 ml) was titrated against $M/10-\text{FeCl}_3$ solution.

Sp. cond. $\times 10^4$.	Vol.	Remarks.
6.66±	0.00 ml	
9.448	0.50	Ppt. forms but dissolves on shaking
10.97	0.75	
12.58	1.00	
14.27	1.25	
16.18	1.50	
17.99	1.75	
21.38	2.25	
25.64	2.75	White turbidity
28.70	3.00	
31.10	3.25	
33.61	3.50	
35.88	3.75	
38.07	4.00	
40.56	4.25	
43.39	4.50	
46.35	4.75	
49.75	5.00	Ppt. settles and supernatant liq. is clear

TABLE IV

System $\text{FeCl}_3-\text{H}_2\text{O}-\text{Na}_2\text{HPO}_4$. $M/50$ -Solution (25 ml) was titrated against $M/10-\text{Na}_2\text{HPO}_4$ solution.

Vol.	pH.	Vol.	pH.
0.00 ml	2.13	7.50 ml	2.55
0.50	*2.10	8.00	2.76
1.00	2.06	8.50	3.04
2.00	2.02	9.00	3.56
3.00	1.94	9.50	4.42
4.00	**1.91	9.75	4.90
4.25	1.91	10.00	5.27
4.50	1.91	11.00	6.03
4.75	1.94	12.00	6.30
5.00	1.96	13.00	6.50
5.50	2.03	14.00	6.60
6.00	2.12	15.00	6.72
6.50	2.24	17.50	6.90
7.00	2.39	20.00	7.00

* Turbidity appears.

** Buff ppt.

Conductometric Study.—Solutions of $M/250$ ferric chloride was titrated against $M/10-(\text{NaPO}_3)_n$ and the specific conductance was plotted against the volume of $(\text{NaPO}_3)_n$ in Fig. 1. The reverse titration was also carried out and plotted in Fig. 3. The corresponding tables (I and III) are also given

Potentiometric Study.—A solution of $M/500$ ferric chloride was titrated against $M/10$ solution of sodium metaphosphate (assuming 102 as molecular weight). The results are plotted in Fig. 2. Fig. 4 (Table IV) shows a titration of $M/50$ solution of ferric chloride against $M/10 \text{Na}_2 \text{HPO}_4$ solution.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

FIG. 3

Analysis of the Precipitates.—The precipitate, which was obtained maximum at the ratio of 1:1.5 [FeCl_3 : (NaPO_3)_n], was filtered and washed for chloride ions repeatedly. The dilutions of ferric chloride were varied from $M/10$ to $M/500$ and (NaPO_3)_n solution was mixed in the above mentioned ratio. The filtrate was analysed quantitatively for Na and Cl. The white precipitate was dried in oven at 120° for 3 to 4 hrs, cooled, and weighed. The weight was corresponding nearly to the calculated value. Dissolution of the precipitate was made by constant boiling with concentrated nitric acid for 10 to 15 minutes. The analyses of the precipitate and filtrate are given below.

FIG. 4

Precipitate:		Found.	Calc.
Iron		27.50%	27.95%
Phosphorus		22.95	23.27
Sodium		Traces	..
Chloride		--	..
Filtrate:			
Chloride	Sodium	Iron	Phosphorus
2%	1%	Traces	Traces

The above observed percentages were found repeatedly for a number of dilutions of ferric chloride.

The precipitate, which was obtained by addition of disodium orthophosphate to ferric chloride solution, was washed and dried. It was brown in colour and was analysed by dissolving in dilute nitric acid.

	Found.	Calc.	Ratio.
Iron	37.2%	37.02%	Fe : P
Phosphorus	20.00	20.04	1 : 1
Sodium	Traces	..	..
Chloride	..	..	..

The filtrate was treated qualitatively and was found to have iron and phosphorus in excess.

One of the authors (V. S. G.) is grateful to the Council of Scientific & Industrial Research, New Delhi, for the award of a junior research fellowship.